

**MAKTABGACHA YOSHDAGI BOLALAR RIVOJLANISHIDA MTT
VA OILA HAMKORLIGINING AHAMIYATI**

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Anotatsiya: Maqolada maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning har tomonlama rivojlantirish jarayonida Maktabgacha ta'lim tashkilotining oila bilan hamkorlikdagi ishlari samarasi yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar : MTT, bilim, oila, soha, kompetensiya, rivojlanish, aloqa, hamkorlik

Значение мтт и семейного партнерства в развитии детей дошкольника

Аннотация: В статье описаны результаты сотрудничества организации дошкольного образования с семьей в процессе всестороннего развития детей дошкольного возраста.

Ключевые слова: МТТ, знания, семья, сфера, компетентность, развитие, общение, сотрудничество.

The importance of kindergarten and family cooperation in the development of preschool children

Annotation: The article describes the results of the preschool education organization's cooperation with the family in the process of comprehensive development of preschool children.

Key words: MTT, knowledge, family, field, competence, development, communication, cooperation

Bugungi kunda ham aynan matabgacha talim tizimiga alohida etibor qaratilmoqda. Bola shaxsini shakllantirib borar ekanmiz, bu jarayonda uning har tomonlama rivojlanishini etiborga olishimiz kerak. Ham jismonan, ham aqlan, ham ruhan rivojlanayotgan bola kelajakda jamiyatga, yurtga foydasi tegadigan shaxs bo'lib yetishadi. Har bir bola tashqi dunyoni xotira, tasavvur, xayol, tafakkur kabi ruhiy jarayonlar yordamida, shuningdek nutq yordamida bilib olish qobitiyatiga ega. Ammo bolalardagi intellekt, ya 'ni ruhiy jarayonlar (xotira, tasavvur, xayol, tafakkur) shunchaki bola organizmining o'sib borishi va takomillashishi bilangina paydo bo'lmay, balki nutqining rivojlanishi bilan chambarchas bog'liq. Bu jayonda maktabgacha talim tashkiloti hamda oila hamkorligi muhim o'rin egallaydi.

Farzand – oilaning quvonchi, ota-onaning tayanchi jamiyatning hayotbaxsh kuchi. Oqil ota-onalar oilada farzand dunyoga kelishi bilan uning tarbiyasini buvisi, buvasi yoki jamoat tarbiya muassasalariga topshirmay bu mas'uliyatli

vazifa bilan o'zlari jiddiy shug'ullanadilar. Ota-onaning tarbiyachilik vazifasi haqida ulug' rus yozuvchisi M.Gorkiy shunday deb yozgan edi: "Bolasini suyishni tovuq ham biladi. Ularni tarbiyalay olmoq esa-qobiliyat va keng hayotiy bilimlarni talab etuvchi davlat miqyosidagi buyuk ishdir. Oilada kun tartibiga rioya qilinmasa, uydagi yumushlar oila a'zolari o'rtasida to'g'ri taqsimlanmasa, oilada ayolga nisbatan noto'g'ri munosabatda bo'linsa, ichkilikbozlik va boshqa illatlar hukm sursa, bunday oilada o'sgan bola yuqori ta'sirchanligi, hayotiy tajribasi kam bo'lganligi sababli voqealarni o'zi to'g'ri baholay olmaydi. Natijada bola indamas, jahldor, qo'pol bo'lib qoladi. Bolani to'g'ri tarbiyalashda uning oldida ota-onaning obro'si yuqori bo'lishi kerak, busiz tarbiya bo'lishi mumkin emas. Ota-onalarning fuqarolik qiyofasi, hayoti, ishlari, yurish-turishi, jamiyat oldida o'z oilasi uchun javobgarlik tuyg'usi ular obro'sining asosidir. Ijtimoiy faoliyatni oilaviy vazifalar bilan birgalikda olib boradigan, bolalarining hayotiga qiziqadigan va ularga mohirlik bilan rahbarlik qiladigan ota-onalar eng obro'li kishilardir. Bularning hammasi ham otaga, ham onaga birdek taalluqlidir.

Oila bilan shaxsan ishlashning eng keng tarqalgan usuli sifatida qo'llanadigan suhbat bolalarni ertalab qabul qilish va kechqurun kuzatish vaqtida o'tkazilishi mumkin. Ular tarbiyachilar bilan ota-onalarni bir-biri bilan yaqinroq tanishishlariga yordam beradi. Tarbiyachining ota-onalar bilan ertalab o'tkazadigan suhbatlari qisqa muddatli bo'ladi uning yaqinlarida yaxshi kayfiyat, tarbiyachiga ishonch hissi paydo bo'lishida kata ahamiyatga ega.

Ota-onalardan bola kechqurun qanday kayfiyatda bo'lganini, qanday uxlaganini, bola o'zini qanday sezganini so'rash foydali. Tarbiyachi ota-onalarga bolalarni bugun guruhda nimalar kutishi haqida qisqacha axborot beradi. Bu narsa bolani kayfiyatini ko'taradi, ota-onani xotirjam qiladi. Ota-onalar bilan kechki suhbatlar ham vaqt jihatidan cheklangan, ota-onalar bilan kechki suhbat paytida tarbiyachi bolaning tashqi ko'rinishiga taalluqli kamchiliklar aytilishi mumkin. Bolani guruhda kunni qanday o'tkazgani, nimalar bilan mashg'ul bo'lgani, o'zini qanday tutgani, nimaga e'tibor berish kerakligi haqida axborot beradi. Ota-onalarni bola tarbiyasida yo'l qo'ygan biror kamchilik va xatosini tahlil qilish uchun ular bilan yanada mufassal suhbat o'tkazish zarurati tug'ilganda vaziyatni tuzatish uchun malakali maslahat hamda tavsiya berish kerak bo'lganda maslahatlar o'tkaziladi. Ota-onalar bilan MTT xodimlarini birgalikdagi faoliyatini tashkil etish va uning mazmuni MTTdagi sharoitlarga bog'liqdir. Birgalikdagi faoliyat kerakli darajada amalga oshiriladigan joyda o'zaro yordam, bir-birini tushunish, topshirilgan ishga javobgarlik holati vujudga keladi. Ota-onalar MTT maydonini ko'kalamzorlashtirish, xonalarni qish mavsumiga tayyorlash, sog'lomlashtirish ishlarini o'tkazishda yordam ko'rsatishlari, bolalarga bayram kostyumlari

tayyorlashda, bolalarni sayohatga kuzatib borishda ishtirok etishlari mumkin. Agar ota-onalar orasida fotosuratchilar, tikuvchilar, rassomlar bor bo'lsa, ular MTTga bevosita yordam ko'rsatishlari kerak. Birgalikda ishni to'g'ri tashkil etish uchun yillik reja tuziladi va ko'rinadigan joyga ilib qo'yiladi. Ota-onalardan qaysi kunlari MTTga kelib yordam berishlari mumkinligini so'rash lozim.

Xulosa o'rnida ta'kidlash joizki, ulg'aygan sari bolalarda aqliy salohiyatining o'sib borishini kuzatish mumkin. Hayotining birinchi o'n yilligida bolalar aqliy faoliyatining eng qiyin davri, ko'plab yangiliklarni o'zlashtirish, his-hayajonga to'la davr bo'ladi.

Bolalarni maktabga tayyorlashda o'qitish usullarini tanlash muhimdir. Eng keng tarqalgan va samarali usul bu didaktik (ta'limiy) o'yinlardir. Bu kattalarning bolaga ta'limiy ta'sirining bir shakli va shu bilan birga maktabgacha yoshdagi bolaning asosiy faoliyati sifatida foydalanishdir.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar

1. Bahodirovna, H. N. (2023). BOSHLANG'ICH SINFLARDA TARBIYA FANINI O'QITISHNING ASOSIY METOD VA VOSITALARI. TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN, 1(5), 332-338.
2. Bahodirovna, H. N. (2023). Methodological Principles of Teaching The Science of " Education" In Primary Classes. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 366-368.
3. Hojiyeva, N. B. (2023). MODERN METHOD IN TEACHING MOTHER LANGUAGE LESSONS-USING THE CACOGRAPHY METHOD. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 434-439.
4. Hojiyeva, N. B. (2023). INCREASING THE INTEREST OF STUDENTS IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING TECHNOLOGY IN PRIMARY GRADES. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 430-433
5. Narziyeva Shahnoza Rustamovna. (2023). DEVELOPING EMPATHY IN STUDENTS. Oriental Journal of Academic and Multidisciplinary Research , 1(3), 127-131. <https://inno-world.uz/index.php/ojamr/article/view/76>
6. Narziyeva Shaxnoza Rustamjon qizi. (2023). PSYCHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE MANIFESTATION OF ADOLESCENT EMPATHY. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 132-134.
7. Shahnoza Rustamovna, N. (2023). UNDERSTANDING EMPATHY: AN ESSENTIAL COMPONENT OF HUMAN CONNECTION. *American*

Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 378–382.

8. Narziyeva, S. (2023). PSYCHOLOGICAL VIEWS ON THE CHOICE OF PROFESSION. *Modern Science and Research*, 2(10), 333-336.

9. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). MILLIY HARAKATLI O'YINLARNING BOLALAR TARBIYASIDAGI IJTIMOIIY-PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI.

10. Sitora Akbarovna Ikromova. (2023). Formation of Ideological Immunity to Destructive Information. *Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies* (2993-2599), 1(9), 50–54.

11. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). Study of the Formation of Ideological Immunity By Foreign and Russian Researchers. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies* (2993-2157), 1(9), 235-239.

12. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). Adolescence during Destructive Behavior Appearances the Problem Learning Condition. *Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies* (2993-2599), 1(9), 105-109.

13. Salomat, G. L. The essence of the content of the concept of digital educational resources and its role in primary education. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*. 2020, Volume: 10, Issue: 5.

14. Gafurovna, L. S., & Pirniyazova, N. V. (2023). A System for Developing The Skills of A Future Primary School Teacher in the Use Of Digital Educational Resources. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies* (2993-2157), 1(9), 258-262.

15. Gafurovna, L. S. (2023). Mechanism for the Use of Digital Educational Resources by Future Primary School Teachers. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies* (2993-2157), 1(10), 123-128.

16. Hikmatovna, M. N. (2023). BOSHLANG'ICH SINFLARDA TEXNOLOGIYA FANINI O'QITISH JARAYONIDA QO'LLANILADIGAN METOD VA VOSITALAR. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 339-344.

17. Maxmudova, N. (2018). THE ROLE OF COMPUTER TECHNOLOGIES IN THE INNOVATIVE TRAINING PROCESS. *Экономика и социум*, (3 (46)), 34-36.

18. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF BEHAVIOR FORMATION IN ADOLESCENTS. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 184-191.

19. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). NEGATIVE AND POSITIVE CHANGES IN ADOLESCENT BEHAVIOR. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 192-197.

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20. Ikromova, S. A. (2023). FACTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF IMMUNITY TO DESTRUCTIVE IDEAS IN ADOLESCENTS. *Innovation in Science, Education and Technology*.

21. Сайфуллаева, Н. Б. (2020). Важные особенности дидактических игр в процессе обучения математике в начальных школах. *In ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ И ВОСПИТАНИЯ* (pp. 60-62).

22. Сайфуллаева, Н. Б., & Мурадова, Я. М. (2020). Пути эффективного использования методов обучения математике в начальных классах. *In EUROPEAN RESEARCH* (pp. 121-123).

23. Oktam's, S. M. (2023). "Methods and Tools of Speech Development of Small Group Children in Preschool Education Organization". *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies* (2993-2157), 1(9), 104–108.

24. O'ktam qizi Buxoro, S. M. (2022). BOLANING NUTQINI RIVOJLANTIRUVCHI O 'YINLAR. *PEDAGOGS jurnali*, 1(1), 484-486.

25. Isomova, F. A. T. Q. (2022). MAKTABGACHA TALIM TASHKILOTLARIDA BOLALARNI MAKTAB TA'LIMIGA TAYYORLASHDA NUTQ O'STIRISH MASHG'ULOTLARINING AHAMIYATI. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(1), 947-949.

26. Isomova Farog'at Tojiddin qizi. (2023). THE CONTENT OF THE FORMATION OF SPEECH AND READING COMPETENCES OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN. *International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development*, 10(11). Retrieved from <https://www.ijmrd.in/index.php/imjrd/article/view/444>.

27. Isomova Farog'at Tojiddin qizi. (2023). MAKTABGACHA TA'LIM TASHKILOTI PEDAGOG-TARBIYACHISINING TA'LIM TARBIYA JARAYONINI REJALASHTIRISH FAOLIYATI. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 1(5), 292–299.

28. Isomova Farog'at Tojiddin qizi. (2023). MODERN IN FORMING SPEAKING COMPETENCES OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN APPROACHES. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies* (2993-2157), 1(10), 347–352.

29. Isomova Farog'at Tojiddin qizi. (2023). INVALIDITY IN CHILD EDUCATION IS THE BASIS OF DEVIANT BEHAVIOR. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies* (2993-2157), 1(10), 342–346.

30. Tursunova, Z. N. (2023). START MODERN PRINCIPLES OF ORGANIZING OUTSIDE THE CLASSROOM IN CLASSROOMS. *American*

Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 494-499.

31. Tursunova, Z. N. (2023). ORGANIZING OUTSIDE THE CLASSROOM IN MOTHER TONGUE SUBJECT. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies* (2993-2157), 1(10), 468-472.

32. Nigora Kozimova Abduqahorovna. (2023). Modern psychological consultation, its types and reasons for applying to it. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies* (2993-2157), 1(9), 129–131. Retrieved from <http://grnjournal.us/index.php/AJPDIS/article/view/1343>

33. Kozimova, N. A. (2023). Techniques and methods used in the process of psychological counseling. *American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies* (2993-2157), 1(10), 338-341.

34. Yulduz, S. (2024). SYUJETLI-ROLLI OYINLARNING BOLA FAOLIYATIDAGI AHAMIYATI. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 2(1), 44-51.

35. Sobirovna, S. Y. (2024). MAKTABGACHA TA'LIMDA NUTQ, MULOQOT OQISH VA YOZISH MALAKALARINING SOHALARI. *TECHNICAL SCIENCE RESEARCH IN UZBEKISTAN*, 2(1), 52-62.

36. Ravshanovna, X. S. (2022). BO'LAJAK O'QITUVCHILAR VA O'QUVCHILAR O'RTASIDAGI MULOQOT JARAYONI VA UNGA QO'YILADIGAN TALABLAR. *Лучший инноватор в области науки*, 1(1), 814-819.

37. Ravshanovna, X. S. (2023). O'qituvchi kasbiy faoliyatida pedagogik muloqot usullarining o'zlashtirish jarayoniga ta'siri va ahamiyati. *Journal of Universal Science Research*, 1(10), 803-816.

38. G'aniyevna, P. R. F. (2022, June). MAKTABGA TAYYORLOV GURUHLARI UCHUN SAVODXONLIKKA O'RGATISH MASHG'ULOTLARIDA, A'HARF-TOVUSHINI O'RGATISH METODIKASI. In *E Conference Zone* (pp. 38-41).